

Formation of organo-mercurio compounds by mercuric acetate oxidation of 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime and 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone

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Abstract : On treatment with mercuric acetate 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime and 2'-aryloxy-5-chloroacetophenone afforded organo-mercurio compounds in excellent yield at room temperature.

Keywords : Organometallic compound, mercuric acetate, oxymercuration-demercuration, allyloxy chloroacetophenone.

Introduction

Organometallic Chemistry is now a very large area, occupying a border line region between organic and inorganic chemistry. A great deal of recent research work has been developed to the synthesis of organometallic compounds. Synthesis of mercury heterocycles is an important work to the synthetic chemists. Easy availability of *o*-allyloxyacetophenone oxime and *o*-allyloxyacetophenone encouraged us to use oxymercuration¹⁻³ and demercuration sequence for the synthesis of corresponding heterocycles. In this connection the reaction of 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime (1) with mercuric acetate, an oxidizing agent having remarkable reactivity towards olefins^{4,5} was initially studied. Thus, when 1 was treated with 1 mole equivalent of mercuric acetate at room temperature it underwent complete reaction within 48 h affording a product in excellent yield (97%), which has been characterized as the mercury compound 3 from its analytical and spectral data as given below.

The organomercury compound 3 was reduced with sodium borohydride in methanol. The reaction gave 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime (1) as the demercuration product. Mercuric acetate is known to undergo reaction with enolisable ketones, where mercuriation takes place at the α -position⁶. This fact along with

the observed facile reaction of 2-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime with mercuric acetate interested us to study the reaction of 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone (2) with the same reagent to explore whether any cyclisation takes place or not. Thus, when 2 was treated with 1 mole equivalent of mercuric acetate in acetic acid at room temperature, it underwent complete reaction within 48 h yielding a product in excellent yield which is characterized as the mercury compound 4 from its analytical and spectral data.

Results and discussion

When compound 1 was treated with 1 molar proportion of mercuric acetate at RT it clearly gave a product (3) within 48 h in excellent yield (97%). Thus, the expected cyclisation took place. The proton integrations in the PMR spectrum of the product formed by the reactions of the substrate with Hg(OAc)₂ in 1 : 1 molar ratio clearly indicate the presence of twenty two protons in 3. The probable mechanistic paths may be delineated to explain the formation of 3 from 1 (Scheme 1).

Possibly, demercuration product 1 was formed from 3 by the following mechanism (Scheme 2).

Mechanistic pathways can be suggested for the formation of 4 from 2 (Scheme 3).

In conclusion, mercuric acetate oxidation technique

Scheme 1

has been utilized to synthesize interesting organometallic compounds of mercury from allyloxyacetophenone oxime and allyloxyacetophenone.

Experimental procedure for oxidation of 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime and 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone by $\text{Hg}(\text{OAc})_2$:

To a mixture of 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime (0.5 mmol) in distilled acetic acid (10 ml), mercuric acetate (0.5 mmol) was added portionwise with shaking to get a homogeneous reaction mixture. The reaction mixture was kept at RT for 48 h. The resulting reaction mixture was poured into water and extracted with chloro-

Note

Scheme 2

form. A high polar residue was obtained in each case which was crystallized from chloroform-petrol when compound 3 was obtained in pure state. Compound 4 was obtained in pure state from 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone by applying similar procedure.

Experimental procedure for sodium borohydride reduction of 3 :

To a solution of 3 (100 mg) in dry methanol excess sodium borohydride was added gradually and the reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 48 h. It was then diluted adding with water, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and extracted with chloroform. The residue obtained after removal of chloroform was chromatographed over silica gel using chloroform as eluent which was then crystallized from chloroform-petrol.

The m.p. of the crystallized product was same with 2'-allyloxy-5-chloroacetophenone oxime (m.p. 112–114 °C).

Compound 3 : m.p. 220–222 °C (colourless needles from chloroform-petrol) (Found : C, 40.22; H, 3.24; N, 3.98. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{22}O_4N_2Cl_2Hg$: C, 40.65; H, 3.41; N, 4.3%); IR (KBr) : 2900, 2840, 1560, 1470, 1390, 1250, 1200, 1180, 1110, 1080, 990, 860, 820, 795, 735 and 705 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (300 MHz, $CDCl_3$) : δ 1.59 (1H, dd, J 12.6 and 6 Hz), 1.76 (1H, dd, J 12.6 and 5.7 Hz, $-CH_AH_BHg-$), 2.47 (1H, s, CH_3), 4.46 (1H, dd, J 10.8 and 3.9 Hz), 4.56 (1H, t, J 10.8 Hz, OC_AH_B-), 4.87–4.92 (1H, m, $>CH-N^+<$), 7.03 (1H, d, J 9.3 Hz, H-9) and 7.29–7.33 (2H, m, H-6 and H-8). [The proton integrations given here are for half of the protons present in the molecule].

Compound 4 : m.p. 134–135 °C (colourless needles

Scheme 3

from chloroform-petrol) (Found : C, 40.08; H, 3.20. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_8\text{Cl}_2\text{Hg}$: C, 40.48, H, 3.40%); IR (KBr) : 2990, 2940, 2900, 1730 (C=O), 1662 (C=O), 1590, 1480, 1400, 1365, 1350, 1270, 1220, 1150, 1090, 940,

900, 840, 800, 750 and 665 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 2.10 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 2.09–2.23 (2H, m, $-\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B\text{Hg}-$), 2.60 (3H, s, COCH_3), 4.09–4.13 (2H, m, $\text{O}-\text{CH}_A\text{H}_B$), 5.54 (1H, m, $>\text{CH}-\text{OCOCH}_3$), 6.90 (1H,

Note

d, J 8.7 Hz, H-3), 7.41 (1H, dd, J 9.0 and 2.7 Hz, H-4), 7.68 (1H, d, J 2.7 Hz, H-6). [The proton integrations given here are for half of the protons present in the molecule].

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